

DIFFERENCES BETWEEN FORMAL AND INFORMAL LETTERS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6560355>

To'xtasinova Durdona Tolibjon qizi

Master's Degree Student, Department of Foreign language and literature, UzSWLU

Abstract: *The article is concerned with the study of comparing and contrasting different features of formal and informal letters. Letters are a form of verbal and written communication, which contains information or message, send by one party to another, to convey the message. It is sent by one party to another, to provide certain important information. There are two types of letters, i.e. formal letters and informal letters. The formal letter is written for business or professional purposes with a specific objective in mind. Previous researches and studies in this area of investigation have been gathered and analyzed. Several points of the issue have been taken into consideration and concluded that there are distinctive differences between formla and informal letters.*

Keywords: *Letter, Formal letter, Informal letter, communication, comparison, written message, information.*

Introduction

A letter is usually defined as a written message sent by one person to another. In other words, a letter is a piece of conversation by post. So, when we transfer any written message through mail, it can be termed as letter.

According to **Oxford Dictionary**, "A letter is a message that is written down or printed on paper and usually put in an envelope and sent to somebody."

"How wonderful it is to be able to write someone a letter! To feel like conveying your thoughts to a person, to sit at your desk and pick up a pen, to put your thoughts into words like this is truly marvelous." Haruki Murakami (Norwegian Wood)

The first recorded letter written by hand was by the Persian Queen Atossa around 500 BC. Little did she know that she was starting a trend that would be followed by generations after her, and this simple activity would turn into an art as well as a tool for change.

Letters have been an integral part of communication for centuries. Famous personalities and commoners alike put pen to paper and poured their hearts out. Parents wrote long letters about life to their children, revolutionaries inspired millions through words scribbled on torn pieces of paper and spies ferreted out little notes holding valuable pieces of information. For a long time, the world depended on letters for information. But, with the advent of technology in the form of e-mails and text messages, letter writing has been reduced to just an art form that few with a fancy

indulge in. In this article, some differences between formal and informal letters are discussed.

Distinctive features of formal and informal letters

Letters are a form of verbal and written communication, which contains information or message, send by one party to another, to convey the message. It is sent by one party to another, to provide certain important information. There are two types of letters, i.e. formal letters and informal letters. The formal letter is written for business or professional purposes with a specific objective in mind. It uses simple language, that can be easy to read and interpret.

On the contrary, informal letters are written to friends and relative for personal communication and uses a casual or an emotional tone. The article excerpt presents you all the important differences between formal and informal letters in a detailed manner.

A formal letter is any letter written in the professional language, with a prescribed format for a formal purpose, i.e. it can be a recommendation letter, enquiry letter, complaint letter, cover letter and so on. All business letters are formal, but vice versa is not possible. Such letters are used for a variety of reasons like a formal invitation, proposal, reference, making a complaint or inquiry, applying for a job. While writing a formal letter one should keep in mind the following things:

- It should be in specified format.
- It should avoid the use of unnecessary words.
- It should be straight to the point.
- It should be relevant and objective.
- It should be complex and thorough.
- It should be polite, even if it is a complaint letter.
- It should be free from any mistakes, i.e. grammatical or spelling.

There are three types of formal letters, i.e. business letters, letters for outlining civic problems and job applications.

An informal letter is the type of letter you would write to someone you know, for example a friend or family member. They're written in a style that is more friendly and familiar in comparison to a [formal letter](#) which follows strict rules about layout and style.

Features of an informal letter

Informal letters have different features in comparison to formal letters. They aren't as rigid in the way they are structured or written. And this means when you write a letter to your friend you can have some fun by breaking the usual letter writing rules.

The way you structure your letter will depend on the type you are writing. But there are a few common features that are noticed when writing informally. These are:

- A friendly opening and close
- A date

- Informal and chatty language
- Written in first person
- Paragraphs
- Addresses of the sender and recipient (depending on the type of letter)

Conclusion

BASIS FOR COMPARISON	FORMAL LETTER	INFORMAL LETTER
Meaning	A formal letter is a letter, written in formal language, in the stipulated format, for official purpose.	A letter written in an friendly manner, to someone you are familiar with, is called informal letter.
Objective	Professional Communication	Personal Communication
Format	Written in prescribed format only.	No prescribed format.
Written in	First person - Business letters, third person - others.	First, second or third person.
Written to	Business, college/institute, employer, organizations, etc.	Friends, family, acquaintances etc.
Voice	Passive	Active
Sentences	Long and complex	hort and simple
Size	Concise	Large or concise
Contractions and Abbreviations	Avoided	Used

So, before start writing letter, first of all, you should identify, Who is your recipient? If you are having a professional relationship with the recipient, then you should go for a formal letter, whereas if the recipient is someone very close to you or you know the recipient well, then the informal letter is the right choice for you.

REFERENCES:

1. Barton, D. , & Hamilton, M. (1998). *Local literacies: Reading and writing in one community*. London: Routledge.
2. Black, R. (2009, May). English-language learners, fan communities, and 21st – century skills. *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*. 52(8). 688-697. doi:10.1598/JAAL.52.8.4
3. Ivanich, R. (1998). *Writing and identity: The discursal construction of identity in academic writing*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
4. Gunnarson, B.L. (1997). The writing process from a sociolinguistic viewpoint. *Written communication*, 24(2), 139-188.
5. Golebiowski, Z. , & Liddicoat , A.J.(2002). The interaction of discipline and culture in academic writing. *Australian Review of Applied Linguistics*, 25(2), 59-71.
6. Flowerdew, J. (1999). Writing for scholarly publication in English: The case of Hong Kong. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 8(2), 123-145.